

ADVANCED MANAGEMENT TECHNOLOGIES AND FOREIGN EXPERIENCES IN DEVELOPING THE MANAGEMENT ACTIVITIES OF LEADERS OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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ABSTRACT

In the modern conditions of globalization and intensification of the educational process, the study of foreign experience in managing preschool educational organizations is of particular importance. This is due to the need to adapt successful practices to the conditions of Uzbekistan in order to improve the mechanisms for developing managerial competence. This section provides a comparative analysis of managerial approaches in different countries in order to identify the best practices that can be adapted and applied in Uzbekistan..

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In the context of globalization, the comparative analysis of the managerial competence of directors of preschool educational organizations provides a unique opportunity to study and adapt foreign practices in Uzbekistan. In the context of the rapid development of the educational process and constantly changing socio-economic conditions, the analysis and implementation of successful international management strategies is becoming increasingly important.

Comparative analysis allows you to determine what managerial approaches are used in different countries, assess their effectiveness, and identify opportunities for adaptation to the conditions of Uzbekistan. This approach is aimed at improving the mechanisms for developing managerial competencies in preschool educational organizations, which will help to improve the overall quality of education. A comparative analysis of managerial approaches in preschool education in different countries is of great interest to Uzbekistan for several reasons:

The study of successful models of managing preschool educational organizations in different countries allows us to identify the key elements that make these systems effective. These can be teaching methods, employee motivation systems, approaches to interaction with parents, or innovative programs for child development.

Comparing different approaches helps to assess which ones are most effective in different contexts. For example, the early childhood development system in Scandinavian countries can provide useful lessons for developing countries in terms of organizing preschool education.

Understanding how aspects of successful foreign practices can be adapted to Uzbek realities helps to create modified methods taking into account the cultural, economic and social characteristics of the country. This includes curriculum adaptation, staff management techniques, and family engagement strategies.

Combining proven and successful management techniques can significantly improve the quality of preschool education in Uzbekistan. This, in turn, will help improve children's readiness for school, which is crucial for the overall development of the country's education system.

An approach aimed at comparative analysis and adaptation of foreign management practices can be a key element of the strategy for improving the effectiveness of preschool education in Uzbekistan. This requires not only the study of foreign experiences, but also a careful analysis of domestic needs and opportunities for changes in local management practices.

The purpose of this comparative analysis is to identify best practices that can be successfully adapted to improve the preschool education system in Uzbekistan. These include management structures, policies, strategies for involving parents and the public, methods of improving staff skills, and innovative approaches to education and parents. The results of the comparative analysis are expected to enrich the understanding of current trends and challenges in the management of preschool educational organizations and provide valuable recommendations for the formation of effective educational policies in Uzbekistan. This study will serve as a basis for the development of improved programs for the training and education of leaders, as well as for the optimization of management processes in preschool educational organizations.

In recent years, the introduction of innovative technologies into management activities has become a priority area of educational management. In particular:

Electronic management systems - digitization of document flow in preschool educational institutions, automation of statistical reports (in the experience of Uzbekistan, the "Preschool Education Information System" has been established).

Project management - development of strategic development projects and their phased implementation.

KPI and competency model - clear criteria for assessing the activities of leaders and educators.

Innovative communication technologies - effective communication between the leader and the team, interactive cooperation with parents.

According to an analysis of foreign experience, the "Kaizen" philosophy is widely used in Japan to develop the managerial competence of leaders, the "Leadership in Early Childhood Education" program is widely used in the United States, and the "Management in Preschool Education" concept is widely used in Russia.

Figure 3. Updated mechanism for implementing advanced management technologies

Diagnostic stage - at this stage, the head of the institution analyzes the current conditions, internal and external factors, resources and team potential. At the same time, management shortcomings and development opportunities are identified. Based on this stage, the head determines the starting point for the development strategy of the institution.

Design and modeling stage - based on the diagnostic results, an innovative management model is developed. This model includes mechanisms and algorithms for the activities of the leader, determines the role of employees and helps to systematically plan the actions of the team.

Implementation stage - the developed innovative technologies are put into practice. At this stage, measures are taken to integrate them into the activities of the pedagogical team, optimize processes and improve the quality of education.

Reflection and development stage - the results of the implemented technologies are evaluated, analyzed on the basis of monitoring, and effective aspects are strengthened. At the same time, the management mechanism is updated and improved, taking into account the identified shortcomings and new opportunities.

This updated mechanism allows the head of a preschool educational organization to systematically and effectively organize his leadership activities, improve the quality of the pedagogical team, and continuously develop innovative approaches.

In our opinion, the training of a head of a preschool educational organization is a continuous professional-educational process aimed at developing the leader's systematic managerial, innovative, and information and communication competencies, strategic decision-making, and the ability to effectively manage the pedagogical team.

For the analysis of the study, we selected countries with highly developed preschool education systems, such as Finland, Japan, and the Netherlands. The main criteria for comparison are: the management structure of preschool educational organizations, methods of motivating and developing staff, as well as the use of innovative technologies in managerial activities. The research methods include the analysis of scientific literature, official documents, as well as interviews with specialists and heads of educational organizations. (See Table 1)

Table 1

The main criteria in developed countries	
Management structure of preschool educational organizations	To study organizational structures that promote effective management and operational activities of preschool educational organizations. This will allow us to understand which structural models are most successful in different cultural and economic contexts.
Employee motivation and development methods	Analysis of strategies and programs aimed at motivating, developing, and retaining qualified staff in a preschool educational organization. This includes studying training, career development, and employee incentive systems.
Using innovative technologies in management activities	Assess how technological innovations are incorporated into management processes and how they impact the quality and availability of early childhood education.

The collected data and analysis allow not only to improve the understanding of effective management practices, but also to make specific recommendations for their adaptation and application in the management of preschool educational organizations in Uzbekistan, which will help to increase the quality and availability of preschool education in the country.

Based on these conclusions, the following recommendations can be offered for adapting foreign experience and improving the management of preschool educational organizations in Uzbekistan:

1. Create and implement comprehensive programs for directors of preschool educational organizations, including the study of advanced international practices, pedagogical management courses, and innovative management modules. Such programs will help prepare leaders capable of effectively managing modern preschool educational organizations.

2. Encourage heads of preschool educational organizations to experiment with new approaches and technologies in management, training, and education. This includes grants for the development and testing of new curricula, as well as pilot projects in preschool educational organizations.

3. Support for directors in their role as pedagogical leaders, which includes not only managing administrative aspects, but also actively participating in the development of curricula, improving the skills of staff, and establishing relationships with parents.

The use of these recommendations will not only improve the quality of management in preschool educational organizations, but also create more favorable conditions for the development of each child, which is the main task of preschool education.

